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THE STRUCTURE AND OPERATION PRINCIPLE OF A PERMANENT MAGNET-ELECTROMAGNET OF AN INDUCTION GENERATOR (1)

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Annotation: The paper presents the structure, the operation principle, the main dynamic characteristics, the electrical circuits of the magnetic systems replacements, the features of the magnetic system, the characteristics and operating points of the permanent magnet-electromagnet of the induction generator.

Keywords: induction, generator, voltage, permanent magnet, characteristic, operating point, electromagnet, electromotive force

Introduction: The task of the permanent magnet-electromagnet of an induction generator (PMEIG) is to provide electrical energy of a sufficient power to the load. And its characteristic is that they perform independently from the external power supply hence are autonomous. The energy of the permanent magnets (PM) is converted into electrical energy based on the conductivity of the magnet system hence on the change of the magnetic flux.

Figure 1 shows the scheme of the principal structure of PMEIG, where 1 is the PM, 2, 2', and 2'' are the induction windings (IW), 3 and 3' are the ferromagnetic cores of the electromagnets, 4 is the magnetic wire, 5 is the ferromagnetic shunt. The movement of the ferromagnetic shunt by X or Z axis changes the conductivity of PMEIG's magnetic field, as a result, the Φ magnetic flux included in the IWs changes, and according to Maxwell's second law, in electromotive force (EMF) is induced, the dimensions of which is calculated by

$$e_{in} = -W_{IW} \frac{d\Phi}{dt},$$

where w_{iw} is the number of the turns winding, $d\Phi$ is the change of the magnetic field flux during the period dt .

Figure 1 – The principal structure of the PMEIG

The research problem: The full structure of the developed PMEIG is shown in Figure 2. 1 is the ferromagnetic shaft, 2 is the bearing, 3 is the plastic lid, 4 is the ferromagnetic plat, 5 are the rotating parallel ferromagnetic shunts deviated by 60 degrees with respect to each other, 6 are the blocks of the electromagnets with 6 IWs in each, 7 are the ferromagnetic cores and 8 are the pole tips, 9 is the ferromagnetic case, 10 is the plastic case, 11 is the block of six axis-magnetized cylindrical PMs with 12 being the IWs surrounding the latter [1, 2].

Figure 2 – The structure of the PMEIG

The rotation of the shaft is passed to the sections of the rigid fixed ferroagnetic shunts. The plastic lids, ferromagnetic plates, the rigid electromagnets fixed on top of them, and the blocks of the PM are fixated due to their rigid connection with the ferromagnetic case.

The ferromagnetic pole tips and cores, ferromagnetic plates, the shaft, and the torso operate as a magnetic wire for the magnetic flux, and the ferromagnetic plate and the torso as a protective screen against the external magnetic fields.

When rotating the shaft passes the rotation to the shunts, the ferromagnetic sections of which are between the pole tips and the PMs and they shunt the PMs and forbid the electric flux from entering the electromagnets.

In that case, the powerlines of each PM's magnetic flux close: air gap-ferromagnetic sector of shunt, after which a part is closed by shaft-ferromagnetic sector of shunt-air gap magnetic chain, and the other part by air gap-ferromagnetic case-air gap-ferromagnetic sector of shunt-air gap magnetic chain. In the case when shunts are in non-ferromagnetic sectional position, the powerlines of magnetic flux close by air gap-pole tip-core-ferromagnetic plate magnetic chain, after which a part is closed by air gap-shaft-air gap-ferromagnetic plate-core-pole tip-air gap magnetic chain, and the other part by ferromagnetic case-ferromagnetic plate-core-pole tip-air gap magnetic chain.

In the two different positions of the shunts, the resistances of the magnetic circuits on the way of each PM's magnetic flux changes. Shunts spin at a certain speed and, as a result, in the corresponding IWs EMF is induced.

Figure 3 shows the interconnected characteristics of average Φ_{PMav} magnetic field flux change in the PM and the e_{inPM} EMF induced in the IW located on top of the PM by time t . And Figure 4 shows the interconnected characteristics of the Φ_{EMav} magnetic flux change in the electromagnet's core and the e_{inEM} EMF induced in the IW by time t . A single PM-electromagnet system is considered.

Figure 3 – Interconnected characteristics of $\Phi_{PMav}(t)$ and $e_{inPM}(t)$

Figure 4 – Interconnected characteristics of $\Phi_{EMav}(t)$ and $e_{inEM}(t)$

As a result of magnetic field analysis, the electrical schemes of PMEIG's magnetic system replacement for the two different shunt positions have been developed (Fig. 5), where R notes the magnetic

resistance of the corresponding area. Thus, R_{δ_1} and R_{δ_2} are the magnetic resistances of the δ_1 and δ_2 air gaps (Fig. 2), R_{EM} is of the pole tip-ferromagnetic cores, R_{fp} is of the ferromagnetic plate, R_1 is of the ferromagnetic plate-shaft haft air gap, R_c is of the case, R_s of the shaft, R_{sh} of the hunt, R_2 of the shunt-case air gap, R_{m2} is of the shunt-shaft area, F_{f1} and F_{f2} are the sources of the fake MMF characterizing the PM. The magnetic fluxes are noted with Φ in the corresponding areas.

Figure 5 – Electrical schemes of the replacement of PMEIG's magnetic system:

a) without a ferromagnetic shunt; b) with a ferromagnetic shunt

For the sake of simplifying the electrical schemes of the magnetic system replacement the following assumptions were made:

- the magnetic resistance of the ferromagnetic details is ignored,
- the scattering magnetic flux in the ferromagnetic details is ignored.

Figure 6 shows the simplified electrical scheme of PMEIG's magnetic system replacement taking into account the mentioned assumptions, where R_{δ} is the magnetic resistance of the δ_1 and δ_2 double air gaps by the shunt positions.

Figure 6 – Simplified electrical scheme of PMEIG’s magnetic system

To construct the features and to determine the operational points of the PM we accept that the material is homogeneous, it is magnetized by the corresponding axis in a homogeneous magnetic field until saturation, and fixation is made.

The PMs in the PMEIG’s system are magnetized outside of the generator’s system. That’s why the parameters in the neutral cross-section of the PM on the B(-H) character turn into $A_0(H_0, B_0)$, and in the poles (e.g. the pole N) turn into $A_N(H_N, B_N)$ because of the scattering fluxes (Fig. 7).

Figure 7 – B(-H) characteristic and operational points of the PM

When the PM is installed into the magnetic system of the PMEIG, due to the δ_1 air gap the conductivity of the magnetic system increases, and the parameters of the PM in the neutral cross-section turn into $A'_0(H'_0, B'_0)$ (moving by the reverse line) and into $A'_N(H'_N, B'_N)$ in the N pole. In the

case of the δ_2 air gap, the corresponding values are $A''_0(H''_0, B''_0)$ and $A''_N(H''_N, B''_N)$, because $\delta_1 > \delta_2$. If we neglect the magnetic losses in the magnetic circuit, and the conductivity of the scattering flows will remain unchanged.

The change in the magnetic field flux $\Delta\Phi_{PM}$ in PM is due to the average value of the difference $B'_0 - B''_0$ and the difference $B'_N - B''_N$. The $\Delta\Phi_{EM}$ magnetic field flux change in the electromagnet's core is conditioned by the B'_N induction value.

Conclusion. The analyzes of the PMEIG structure, working principles, positions of the operating points of the corresponding areas of the magnetic system, and the PM are a base to design a mathematical apparatus of a magnetic system calculation.

Gratitude

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